

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

THE IMPACT OF VIRUSES AND THE TREATMENT PROCESS ON PSYCHOLOGICAL HUMAN CONDITION

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Abstract

As many experts note, patients who survived outpatient treatment have depressed mood and anxiety, which are some of the symptoms of a post-traumatic state in the phase of intoxication that accompanies any disease, and even more so infectious diseases. After prolonged treatment, many people experience an acute disturbance of mental activity, and their perception of reality is disturbed. Behavior is concerned, and emotional reactions do not correspond to the actual situation. And there is also developmental coordination disorder, accompanied by a complete stupor or increased arousal.

Keywords: treatment, infections, viruses, psychology, influence, psychotherapy, behaviour, disorders, functions, application.

Recently, infections have been spread all over the world that no one heard about 20 years ago, which leads to intoxication, and oxygen starvation of the brain, which in turn causes an exacerbation of diseases of the neurological and psychiatric spectrum. And in older people, emotional and intellectual impairment is exacerbated. COVID-19, the more common infection of recent times in many infected and people with weak immune systems, requires long-term outpatient treatment, which itself causes a violation of a person's mental state. All this is accompanied by a violation of consciousness functions, hallucinogenic knowledge, and fear of the future. Anxiety-depressive behavior disorder, panic attacks, and obsessive-compulsive disorder are commonly manifested. [6].

A person suffering from an infectious disease experiences a mental breakdown due to long-term treatment, which can provoke a relapse and complicate the treatment process. For example, taking antibiotics and constant conditions in a hospital can cause psychosis in a patient with schizophrenia, manifested in hallucinations and inappropriate behavior, fears, and panic attacks. [2;5].

Any infection leads to the development of not only mental disorders but also the appearance of chronic diseases. With COVID-19, hypoxia, a lack of oxygen, occurs, which leads to a disruption in the nutritional function of the brain, a violation of behavior and self-control, and self-criticism. As history, which we all witness, has shown, the pandemic creates instability in society; this manifests itself in both economic and social factors. Mass illness, quarantine, social restrictions, and constant news about the death of loved ones and

relatives all lead to psychosis, which manifests itself depending on the state of the body in various forms, such as depression, anxiety, sleep disturbance, fear that never leaves you, and apathy.

Researchers state that the outbreak of any pandemic or epidemic affects not only the patients' mental state but also the people in their environment. Thus, approximately one in six, under the influence of the epidemic, developed symptoms of moderate and severe depression, and one in three showed signs of increased anxiety of varying severity. [3;5].

We, in turn, conducted a questionnaire survey of teachers and students on the topic: in your opinion, how much does the long-term treatment of infectious diseases negatively affect the human psyche? Teachers and students of higher educational institutions in Azerbaijan and Turkey took part in the survey. Survey participants did not unequivocally answer our questions; some (54%) note that the symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder associated with long-term treatment lead to psychological depression, unwillingness to continue their work, study, etc. Another group of respondents (34%) believe that the pandemic worsens their mood, there is uncertainty about the future, and the course of mental disorders in such people leads to prolonged apathy. The next group of respondents (12%) note that the pandemic mentally affects not only the patients themselves but also negatively on their environment. According to our interviewees, 65% of family members who lived with patients with COVID-19 can also observe symptoms of anxiety about their health and signs of developing apathy and depression.

From the above, we can conclude that the more difficult the treatment of infectious diseases, the greater the possibility of a future complication of mental disorders, and the degree of rapid recovery decreases. As a social survey of passers-by shows, in a third of people who have recovered after long-term treatment, changes in behavior and complications in the function of the psyche (apathy, deterioration of memory, thinking, etc.) can be observed.

Many people who have been ill with infectious diseases say that they experience the unwillingness to continue to fight, constant fatigue and malaise, difficulty in choosing words, memory impairment, decreased concentration, etc. They describe their condition after being treated for COVID-19 as a blur in relationships and the perception of everyday things. Experts studying this problem report that many people constantly experience headaches and dizziness, their sense of smell and taste deteriorates, and muscle weakness appears. [1;7].

Our research confirms that many COVID-19 survivors have post-traumatic stress disorder, and for many, this manifests itself in the form of depression and anxiety disorder, impaired self-esteem, and self-criticism, which leads to disruption of life in society. In addition, our survey shows that 49% of people develop behavioral inhibition and chronic fatigue as a result of long-term treatment.

Now I would like to note what is happening at the chemical level; this is a complex multi-level process of active interaction of infectious pathogenic agents with microorganisms, characterized by the development of the so-called complex of typical pathological reactions, meaning there are systemic functional shifts, resulting in a disorder of the hormonal status, specific immunological defense mechanisms and factors of nonspecific resistance of the body to the effects of various infections. There is a violation of the chemical nutrition of nerve cells which is very hard to recover from. The reason for everything is toxic damage to the central nervous system. The so-called damage to the nervous system, pathogenesis, - leads to molecular disorders and disruption of the activity of many body functions.

In such a situation, it is necessary to use drugs that improve the metabolism of the central nervous system and restore the nutrition of neurons; these are cerebrolysin, nootropic drugs, multivitamins, ATP, nicotinic acid, large doses of ascorbic acid.

In addition to pharmaceutical treatment, it is necessary to restore physical activity. Examples are primarily physical activity, training, and yoga. The rehabilitation process will certainly not be easy, but the positive effect will show its results. Those who have recovered from infectious diseases also need cognitive and psychological rehabilitation-the work of a clinical psychologist is necessary. The rehabilitation process

takes place after recovery; it is necessary to restore cognitive activity, behavior, and concentration, get rid of anxiety, depression, and post-traumatic stress disorders, restore sleep, and thereby get rid of chronic fatigue.

As we noted, practical cognitive-behavioral rehabilitation is necessary. It should include work on the correction of memory, and attention, solving logical problems, and psychotherapy to restore behavior. As a result, the emotional background will normalize, and the person will get rid of apathy, anxiety, stress, and, most importantly, depression. Psychotherapy will help people who have undergone long-term inpatient treatment reduce social isolation.

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